

Serpentine and Serpentinization of Ultramafics, Mwe Taung Area, Kalay Township, Chin State

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Abstract

The study area is situated in the northern portion of Chin State, about 20 miles (32 km) north of Kalaymyo, Sagaing Region. It is bounded by the East Longitude 94° 00' to 94° 03' and North Latitude 23° 22' to 23° 30', which fall in one inch topographic map no. 84 I/3. The total area is coverage over 27 square miles (43 km²). Mwetaung Hill of the study area lies prominently on the eastern flank of the northern Chill Hills. It is almost entirely made up of ultramafic igneous bodies. In the study area, ultramafic rocks of peridotite, harzburgite, lherzolite, serpentinite are mainly distributed. Harzburgite is the most abundant rock type and it is widely distributed throughout the whole area. Lherzolite is found in most places and wehrlite occurs a few places. Serpentinite is exposed in the southeastern flank of Mwetaung. Lateritic soil is widely distributed around the road section and it is mainly exposed at the upper part of Mwetaung Hill. The most rock units of study area are completely serpentinized. According to their physical appearance and microscopic features, there are three types of serpentinites: massive serpentinite, sheared serpentinite and cross-fiber serpentinite. The main serpentine minerals are lizardite, antigortie and chrysotile. The texture of serpentine studied in thin section can be divided into: pseudomorphic textures belong to lizardite, antigortie appears to have a non-pseudomorphic texture. Chrysotile is formed as serpentine veins which were observed as chrysotile asbestos cross-fiber veins, chrysotile asbestos slip-fiber veins and non-asbestiform veins respectively. Serpentine minerals are the dominant phase, comprising more than 90% of the mode of the most ultramafic rocks equilibrated at temperature below about 500°C, and then serpentine minerals; lizardite, antigortie and chrysotile are stable in temperature between 300°C to 500°C. The time of serpentinization is Early Cretaceous because it is related to the time of emplacement of the ultramafic body.

Introduction

Location and Size of the Study Area

The study area is situated in the northern portion of Chin Province, about 20 miles (32 km) north and slightly west of Kalaymyo. It is bounded by the East Longitude 94° 00' to 94° 03' and North Latitude 23° 22' to 23° 30'. The research area is bounded by vertical grids 470 to 540 and horizontal grids 040 to 860, in the northwestern corner of topographic map no.84 I/3 of Burma Survey Department. The total area is coverage over 27 square miles (43 km²). Mwetaung hill is about 14 km in length and 3.2 km in width. Location map of the study area is shown in fig.1.

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Before field works, one inch to one mile scale topographic map was enlarged into two times, four times and eight times respectively, for data plotting and used as a base map. All traverse lines were measured by tape and compass traverse method by using Brunton compass. Representative ore and all rock samples from various rock units were taken with the aid of GPS (Global Position System), German-78, satellite. All such observable measured data were plotted on the eight inch to one mile scale topographic map.

Laboratory Techniques

Firstly, the representative samples of the major rocks units are chosen and divided into two portions: one for analysis and the other for reference. Thin sections were prepared for detailed petrographic studies. Mineral composition was determined by point counting modal analysis. X ray powder diffraction method (XRD) was applied for identification of mineral species.

Regional Geologic Setting

The Western Ranges or the Indoburman Ranges extends from the East Himalayan Syntaxis region southward along the eastern side of the Bay of Bengal up to the Andaman Sea, comprising Naga Hills Tract in the north, the Chin Hills in the middle and the Rakhine (Arakan) Yoma in the South (Dr Win Swe, 2012). Some ultramafic bodies such as Mwetaung, Bhopi-Vum, Webula and other small bodies are exposed as exotic blocks. They are part of the Indoburman Ranges and their trends are approximately N-S.

Hutchison (1975) divided two ophiolite lines in Myanmar, namely Mandalay-Jade Mine Line and Naga Hill Line. The study area is situated in Naga Hill Line by Hutchison. Recently, Hla Htay (2000, 2004) divided the ophiolites in Myanmar into three belts from west to east, namely Western Ophiolite Belt (WOB), Central Ophiolite Belt (COB), and Eastern Ophiolite Belt (EOB). Among three belts of ophiolite, ophiolite of the Kalaymyo area is included in the Western Ophiolite Belt and occurrences from south to north are Laymyethna area, Ledi area, NW of Mindon area, Minbu area, Kanpletlet area, Webula area and Mwetaung

area. In general, almost all of the ophiolite belts reported ever are dismember incomplete ophiolite related to subduction (Fig.2).

The area is located in Western Ophiolite Belt that starts from Naga Hills in the north, through Chin Hills as Mwetaung, Webula, Kanpetlet to Rakhine ranges of Minbu, Mindon, Laymyethna and Nyathaing Chaung in the south, forming a narrow linear belt about 813 miles (1300 km) in length and about 13 miles (20 km) in width (Hla Htay, 2002, 2004). It is believed to be dismembered incomplete ophiolite belt, consisting of ultramafic rocks, pillow lava, basic dykes, spilite, and radiolarian chert, small amounts of limestone and flysch-type sedimentary rocks with nickel and chromite mineralization.

Mwetaung hill of the study area lies prominently on the eastern flank of the northern Chin Hills. It is almost entirely made up of ultramafic igneous bodies. It is bounded on the west and north by ranges of the highly folded Pane Chaung Group and by alluvial plain which overlies folded molasses of the Innerburman Tertiary Basin on the east. Mwetaung ultramafic complexes are not continuous with Bhopi Vum and Webula in the south but show a tectonic alignment along the eastern foothills of the Chin Hills. The regional geological map of study area is shown in (Fig.3).

the Study Area (Dr Thidar Win, 2014)	Rock Sequences of
Age	Unit
Holocene	Alluvium
Pleistocene	Terrace Fan Laterite
Cretaceous-Eocene	Ophiolites (ultramafics, mafic, dykes volcanic)
Pre-Cretaceous	Yazagyo metamorphic
Triassic	Pane Chaung Group

Result and Discussion

Major rock units of study area

Rock Units	Age
Sedimentary Rock	
Chert	
Igneous Rocks	
Wehrlite and Serpentinized Wehrlite	
Lherzolite and Serpentinized Lherzolite	<i>f</i> Early Cretaceous
Harzburgite and Serpentinized Harzburgite	
Dunite and Serpentinized Dunite	<i>J</i>

Igneous Rocks

Dunite and Serpentinized Dunite

In the study area, dunite can be observed on both Mwetaung and Phataung. The rock shows dark brown color on weathered surface. Dunite is distinguished from harzburgite by its color, smooth surface and compactness (Fig 4) & (Fig 5). It is occurred as fine to medium grained texture. It is always found as massive boulders which have several joint sets. Mwetaung dunite is characterized by strong serpentinization. Dunite can also contain a small amount of orthopyroxene and clinopyroxene. It consists mainly of olivine with disseminated chromite.

Fig 2. Ophiolite belts of Myanmar (after Hla Htay, 2002, 2004)

Fig 3. Regional Geological map of study area and its environs (Source: Myanmar Geosciences Society (2014))

Microscopically, this unit is mainly composed of olivine and minor amount of orthopyroxene, clinopyroxene, serpentine and opaque minerals. The mineral constituents of these rock units which are mainly composed of olivine is 64.79% to 89.69%, orthopyroxene is less than 1.88%, clinopyroxene is 3.02% to 6.12%, serpentine is 1.04% to 23.76% and opaque mineral is 4.38% to 5.33%. Olivine is the most abundant mineral in dunite. It is usually occurred as anhedral polygonal forms and colorless under plane polarized light. It shows second order reddish brown to blue color in between crossed nicol. The sizes of olivine are about 2.5 mm to 3mm. It is not distinct in cleavage and common irregular fracture. It is highly altered to serpentine along fracture (Fig 6).

Orthopyroxene (Enstatite) is found as subhedral to anhedral form. It is colorless under plane polarized light and between crossed polars it shows first order interference color. It has parallel extinction.

Clinopyroxene (Diopside) is shown green color under plane polarized light and yellowish red to blue color under crossed polars. It shows incline extinction.

Chromite occurs as disseminated and opaque grains interstitial to olivines. It has somewhat idiomorphic forms. It shows pull apart structure. **Harzburgite and Serpentinized Harzburgite**

This unit is the main rock type of the Mwetaung-Phataung area and widely distributed at Mwetaung hill. Most exposures are found as medium to coarse-grained, massive boulders and highly jointed with rough surface. The rock is dark greenish grey to black color on fresh surface and mostly deep black color on weathered surface. Sometimes, isolated coarsegrained crystals of olivine and pyroxene are well observed on the surface. Some harzburgite are partially serpentinized to form serpentinized harzburgite. This unit gives dark greenish grey fresh color and reddish brown to pale yellowish brown color on weathered surface (Fig.7 & 8). Under the microscope, it is medium to coarse-grained with allotriomorphic granular texture (Fig.9). It is mainly composed of olivine and orthopyroxene. The minor amount of clinopyroxene, serpentine and chromite. According to modal composition, the rock is approximately made up of olivine is 37.15% to 80.39%, orthopyroxene is 6.01% to 10.06%, clinopyroxene is 2.19 to 12.93%, serpentine is 36.82% and opaque is 7.08% to 7.35%. Olivine occurs in granular form and the size is ranging from 0.5mm to 2mm. It is not distinct in cleavage and common in irregular cracks. It has parallel extinction. It shows second order yellowish red to brown color in between crossed polars Orthopyroxene (Enstatite) occurs as subhedral to anhedral grain. It has two set of cleavage interesting at right angle and fairly high relief. It shows colorless to light yellow color in under plane polarized light and brownish yellow to light grey color in between crossed polars. In this rock the component of orthopyroxene is more than the clinopyroxene. Exsolution nature of orthopyroxene and clinopyroxene are also observed (Fig 10). Rim texture of secondary amphibole occurs along the margin of orthopyroxene. It is characterized extinction. The extinction angle is high about 30°.

Clinopyroxene (Diopside) is founded as two sets of cleavage and incline extinction. It shows second order interference color between cross nicol and pale green color in under plane polarized light.

Chromite grains are opaque under the microscope. They are usually seen as accessory minerals in this rock types. Chromite is scattered throughout the harzburgite mainly in the interstitial spaces between the olivine and pyroxene megacrysts. Serpentine are founded as secondary minerals. Frequently serpentine occurs along cracks and fractures in olivine and pyroxene.

Fig.4. Dunite exposed at the Mwetaung Hill. (Facing due E) (N 23° 29' 06.88", E 94° 01' 38.28")

Fig.5. Serpentinized Dunite exposed at the Phataung. (Facing 278°) (N 23° 29' 08.87", E 94° 01' 43.49")

Fig.6. Photomicrograph of dunite showing olivine (ol) with irregular fractures and it shows second order interference color and disseminated chromite (cr) (N 23° 29' 06.88", E 94° 01' 38.28")

Lherzolite and Serpentinized Lherzolite

In the field, harzburgite and lherzolite are very similar both in their color and in the nature of exposures. Lherzolite is dark green color on fresh and black color on weathering. They are highly weather, massive, jointed, hard and compact.

Wehrlite and Serpentinized Wehrlite

A small patch of serpentinized wehrlite is found in the Mwetaung. They are highly weather and strongly serpentinized. They occur as pale green color on weather surface and dark green color on fresher.

Sedimentary Rock

Chert

Chert occurs as massive, highly weathered. The grain size is very fine-grained nearly glass texture (Fig.11). Chert is mainly composed of cryptocrystalline aggregates of chalcedonic silica. Under the microscope, they are very fine grained (Fig.12). Quartz is colorless in under plane polarized light and first order gray color is observed in between crossed polar.

Fig.7

Fig.8

Fig.7. Harzburgite exposed at the Mwetaung Hill.(Facing 75°)(N 23° 23' 56.72", E 94° 01' 09.95")

Fig.8. Serpentinized Harzburgite exposed at the Mwetaung Hill.(Facing due S)(N 23° 25' 54.26",E 94° 02' 05.26")

Fig.9

Between XN

Fig.9

Between XN

Fig.9. Photomicrograph of harzburgite showing allotriomorphic granular texture of olivine (ol),orthopyroxene (opx) and clinopyroxene (cpx) and opaque mineral chromite (cr) (N 23° 29' 51.08", E 94° 02' 13.26")

Fig.10

Between XN

Fig.10

Between XN

Fig.10. Photomicrograph of Exsolution nature of orthopyroxene and clinopyroxene are also observed in harzburgite.

Fig.11. Chert has deep black weathered color and reddish yellow in fresh surface and exposed in the southern part of Phataung. (Facing due W) (N 23° 29' 06.35", E 94° 01' 41.09")

Fig.12. Photomicrograph showing very fine-grained cryptocrystalline quartz (qtz) is aggregated in chert (N 23° 29' 06.35", E 94° 01' 41.09")

Fig.13. The result of IUGS classification of ultramafic rocks of the study area are shown in this figure.

Serpentine Minerals and Serpentinization of Ultramafic Rocks

Types of Serpentine

Serpentine is highly weathered and altered mostly from peridotite. They have been found especially at Mwetaung. The good exposures can be seen on the southeast and northeast ridge of the Mwetaung Hill. This rock shows pale green, dark green and greenish grey on weathered surfaces and fresh surface show green color. They can be occurred as three main types of serpentinites in the study area by their physical appearances. They are massive serpentinite, shear serpentinitized and cross-fiber serpentinite.

Massive Serpentinite

This serpentinite occurs as massive boulder within the inner part of ultramafic body. They are generally dark green, sometime with apple-green blotches or streak. The weathered color of these rock is greenish gray, or sometimes reddish (Fig.14). It was formed from the alteration of dunite, harzburgite, lherzolite and wehrlite. The fresh sample shows dark green color.

Sheared Serpentinite

Sheared serpentinite appear to be developed in places where there has been tectonic movement, for example, along fault zones. They are mostly found as high-rising cliffs. This type is characterized by its smooth shiny surfaces and variations in pale green to yellowish green. In the study area, along the faulted contact zone, sheared serpentinite occur, especially at Mwetaung. (Fig.15)

Cross-fiber Serpentinite

Cross-fibre serpentinites occur as numerous veins that may be on a microscopic scale. These veins appear to be restricted to the areas of undeformed blocky serpentinites. Some slip-fiber (sheared) serpentine may have originally been cross fiber that was deformed and recrystallized during shearing. Their color is commonly pale green to pale yellow green (Fig.16).

Fig.14

Fig.15

Fig.14. Massive Serpentinite exposed at hill sides of Mwetaung.(Facing 312°)(N $23^\circ 23' 14.71''$, E $94^\circ 01' 31.39''$)

Fig.15. Sheared serpentinite exposed in the northeastern part of Phataung.(Facing 95°)(N $23^\circ 29' 42.14''$,E $94^\circ 01' 52.22''$)

Fig.16. Outcrop nature of cross-fiber serpentinite. Facing 155° (N $23^\circ 23' 17.47''$, E $94^\circ 01' 30.30''$)

Textures of Serpentine Minerals

Texture of serpentinites observed in thin sections can be divided into three types. They are;

- (a) Pseudomorphic texture formed after olivine, pyroxene
- (b) Non-pseudomorphic texture formed after the same primary minerals
- (c) Serpentine veins

Pseudomorphic Texture (Mesh Texture)

Most of the massive type serpentinite shows pseudomorphic (mesh texture). Olivine alters along fracture and grain boundary to form pseudomorphs composed of mesh texture (Fig 17). Hourglass textures were formed to be composed of lizardite. In mesh texture consists of mesh rim and mesh center. Most of mesh rim are composed of γ -serpentine were form composed of possibly lizardite. Isotropic serpentine occurs as mesh center (Fig. 18), which is lizardite. Lizardite is the most common mineral in massive serpentinite. The lizardite in the mesh rims occur as apparent fibres lying at a high angle to the original fracture in the olivine. Lizardite replaces orthopyroxene and clinopyroxene and occurs as veins. Lizardite appears in the mesh rim as two lizardite plates lying on either side of the central fracture. Serpentine pseudomorphs after pyroxene are generally called bastite. In enstatite-bastite, serpentinization begins at grains boundaries and fracture, flow along cleavage and parting. They yield γ or α serpentine apparent fiber or lath lying parallel to the original cleavage. Orthopyroxene tend to alter to γ -serpentine bastite.

Clinopyroxene is less serpentinized than orthopyroxene. Some clinopyroxene bastite has been replaced by long thin zones of γ -serpentine apparent fibers along cleavage planes or orthopyroxene exsolution lamella. They may be yield γ -serpentine bastite. Pyroxene bastite replaced by the antigorite was found as blade or patches.

Brucite and magnetite coexist in thin section as minor accessory minerals. As serpentinization process, magnetite form as coarsed-grains and concentrate at the mesh center. At later stage, the magnetite migrates out of the mesh, form cross cutting vein lets. The brucite is characterized reddish brown in color.

Fig.17. Olivine (ol) alters along fracture and grain boundary to form pseudomorphs composed of mesh texture of lizardite (li).

Fig.18. Mesh texture of lizardite (li) which consists of mesh rim and mesh center.

Non-pseudomorphic Texture

Non-pseudomorphic textures are formed either through the recrystallization of pseudomorphic serpentine texture or directly through the serpentinization of primary olivine, and pyroxene. Non-pseudomorphic texture can be divided into interpenetrating texture and interlocking texture. The serpentine grains in both are anhedral and mutually interfere, but tend to be elongate in interpenetrating texture and equant in interlocking texture.

Interpenetrating Texture

Interpenetrating textures are composed of elongate blades, flakes or plates that form a tight penetrating fabric. Interpenetrating texture usually begins to develop as isolated flakes or blades or fan-shaped bundles of blades (Fig. 19 & 20). Interpenetrating texture is composed of antigorite which is optically characterized y-serpentine. The optical identification of serpentine minerals is shown in table 1.

Interlocking Texture

Interlocking textures are composed of irregular, equant sometimes spherulitic grains. Some of these textures have been described as rosette serpentine and radial fiber bundle serpentine. The y-serpentine are composed of antigorite with brucite. **Serpentine Vein**

Serpentine veins occur along fractures and joint planes. The fractures may pitch, swell and branch. They have been sheared. They have often been subjected to slip. The slip vein occurs by sheared affect.

Chrysotile Asbestos Cross-fiber Veins

Chrysotile asbestos has developed in fractures. The chrysotile appears as y-serpentine (Table.1). The fibers in small veins tend to lie normal to the walls and extend from one wall to another. Chrysotile fibers are parallel extinction but some complex extinction develops in cross-fiber veins (Fig.21 & 22).

Chrysotile Asbestos Slip-fiber Veins

Slip fiber veins composed of parallel to subparallel fiber of y-srpentine. Chrysotile was identified as main phase.

Non-asbestiform Veins

These veins may be pseudofibrous, splintery, columnar, and banded. The extinction may be undulating. The serpentine was identified as a or y-serpentine.

Table 1. Optical identification chart for serpentine minerals

Texture	Optical character	Mineral
<u>Pseudomorphic Texture</u>		
Mesh rim	γ	Lizardite, antigorite or brucite
Mesh center	Isotropic	Lizardite+brucite
Hourglass texture	α	Lizardite+brucite
<u>Non-pseudomorphic Texture</u>		
Interlocking	γ	Chrysotile and /or lizardite or antigorite+brucite
Interpenetrating	γ	Antigorite
<u>Vein texture</u>		
Cross-fiber vein	γ	Chrysotile
Slip vein	γ	Chrysotile and/or Lizardite

Fig.19. Interpenetrating textures of antigorite (ant) composed of elongate blades, flakes or plates that form a tight penetrating fabric and chrysotile (chr) vein.

Fig.20. Hourglass texture of lizardite (li), and Interpenetrating textures compose of antigorite.

Fig.21. The chrysotile (chr) fibers in small veins tend to lie normal to the walls and extend from one wall to another.

Fig.22. Non-asbestiform veins may be pseudofibrous, splintery, columnar, and banded

Process of Serpentinization

The reaction; Forsterite + water = serpentine + brucite (1) occur at 380°C at 2 kbar (Johannes (1968)). Forsterite + talc + water $\leftrightarrow$ serpentine (2) occur at 460°C. They are inductions froms of Yoder (1952) and Chernosky (1971, 1975) that the upper stability limits of serpentine is raised by the presence of Al. Possible reaction are:

The serpentinization of diopside and tremolite involves the consideration that either silicon must be removed or an extraneous source of magnesium.

Serpentinization process are divided into eight types depending on the condition involve, or do not involve, rising temperature, presences of substantial shear, and neuclation of antigorites (Wick and Whittaker,1977). This modal provides eight distinguishable regimes in terms of all combination of the following three alternatives;

- (a)(i) falling temperature
- (ii) rising temperature
- (b)(i) absence of substantial shearing
- (ii) presence of substantial shearing
- (c)(i) nucleation of antigorite
- (ii) no nucleation of antigorite

The observed textures of serpentine of investigated area may be classified in terms of the types of process that would be expected to produce them according to type 1, 3 and 5.

Type 1: In this type; pseudomorphic antigorite after olivine, the veins associated with these texture are composed of antigorite. The antigorite texture in a similar environment is non-pseudomorphic (Varlakov, 1975).

Type 3: The serpentinization of olivine by this process lead to the formation of mesh rim by a steadily advancing front of serpentinization that produce reasonably well-crystallized and crudely oriented lizardite (Wicks & Zussman, 1975; Wicks et al. 1977). Pure hourglass textures occur most frequently in association with Type 5 texture, suggesting that the formation of both is promoted by higher temperatures. The remnant olivine fragments may subsequently serpentinize to produce mesh centers of poorly crystalline, fine-grained, semi-randomly to

randomly oriented grains of lizardite (Wicks & Zussman, 1975) with possibly minor chrysotile (Cressey & Zussman, 1976). This mesh center serpentinization takes place simultaneously throughout the olivine remnant, in contrast to the advancing front of serpentinization that produces the mesh rims and pure hourglass texture. Where brucite is present, there is a strong tendency for it to occur, with lizardite, in the mesh centers surrounded by lizardite mesh rims. Orthopyroxenes also alter to lizardite pseudomorphs. Primary clinopyroxene has also been found in this study to be altered to lizardite. According to the calculations and observations of Evans & Trommsdorff (1970), diopside forms a stable assemblage with serpentine (Fig.23). The diopside in equilibrium with the antigorite is of significant different composition from the primary diopside (Peters, 1968), so one could expect the latter to become unstable during serpentinization. The lizardite + secondary diopside pair has not been clearly established for Type 3 serpentinization although diopside is present as a product of this serpentinization process. The vein associated with these textures are composed of lizardite and/or chrysotile (both fibrous and non fibrous) with or without brucite, but the present of significant amounts of chrysotile asbestos veins can be attributed.

Type 5: Interlocking non-pseudomorphic textures or veins of chrysotile form through the recrystallization of lizardite pseudomorphic texture. At the earliest stages the lizardite pseudomorphs are still recognizable, but chrysotile can be detected as a component of the pseudomorphs. As recrystallization advances, the pseudomorphs after olivine are rapidly obliterated, but bastites are often slightly more resistant. Relict primary minerals may be altered to crude chrysotile pseudomorphs, often with brucite, which may then be partly obliterated by the developing interlocking textures. Chrysotile asbestos veins associated with non-asbestiform vein of chrysotile. Spherulitic interlocking textures of multilayer lizardite may also form in serpentinization of this type, through the recrystallization of lizardite±brucite mesh texture and lizardite –brucites, particularly in zones adjacent to multilayer lizardite veins. The development of these more complex polytypes is so closely associated with bastites that their formation might be through to be due to the release of aluminium from the pyroxene during serpentinization.

Condition of Serpentinization

Ultramafic rocks are prone to low-temperature metamorphism and alteration. This is the case, because their constituent high P-T phases, at near surface and low-temperature condition, are far from their field of stability. In addition, mantle rocks are rather dry, and the upper levels of the crust are generally permeated with water, which readily combines with the anhydrous phases of the mantle rocks to produce new hydrous phases. In those kinds of metamorphism, hydrous phases such as tremolite, talc, anthophyllite and serpentines are produced by metamorphism of ultramafic rock types. Although serpentine minerals were mentioned among these minerals previously because they are the dominant phase, comprising more than 90% of the mode of most ultramafic rocks equilibrated at temperature below about 500°C, and because serpentine is a nearly constituent of crustal ultramafic rocks.

Serpentinization is the process or process by which ultramafic or mafic rock are transformed into serpentinites. These process produce the three main varieties of serpentine that complete the serpentinites; lizardite, chrysotile, and antigorite. Lizardite, a planer-structured serpentine and chrysotile, a cylindrically structured serpentine, are polymorphs with the composition $Mg_3Si_2O_5(OH)_3$. Antigorite is compositionally (as well as structurally) distinct, with Mg/Si value somewhat less than the 1.5 of lizardite and chrysotile. Antigorite is generally stable at higher temperature more than the later two phases and revealed by the petrogenetic grid in (Fig.23). Inasmuch as alpine ultramafic rocks are composed primarily of one or more of the Mg rich varieties of olivine, orthopyroxene and clinopyroxene, serpentinization may result essentially from the addition of water.

emplacement of the ultramafic body; therefore, the time of serpentinization is Early Cretaceous.

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References

- Bannert, D., Bosun, W., Einfalt, H.C., Hagen, D., Hindle, R., Mollat, H., Schwarz, G., Than Htay, Wagner, B., and Ruder, B.J., (1982): Eastern Chin Hill and Arakan Mineral Survey (ECAMS), Final Report, Phase I, Technical cooperation, Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources, Hannover, FRG.
- Banner, D., Sang Lyein, A., and Than Htay (2011): The Geology of the Indoburman Ranges, Hannover, p.101.
- Bender, F., (1983): Geology of Burma. Borntraeger, Berlin. 293p.
- Chhibber, H.L., (1934): Geology of Burma, Macmillan, London, 538p.
- Chuan-Liu and et.al, (2016), they are studied the age of Myanmar Ophiolites including the Kalaymyo Ophiolite.
- Cressey, B. A. & Zussman, J. (1976): Electron microscope studies of serpentinite. Can. Mineral. 14, p.307-313.
- Coleman, R.G., (1977): Ophiolites, Berlin, Springer-Verlag. 229p.
- Evans, B. W. & Trommsdorff, V. (1970): Regional metamorphism of ultramafic rocks in the central Alps: Paragenesis in the system CaO-MgO-SiO₂-H₂O. Schweiz. Mineral. Petrog. Mitt. 50, p.481-492.
- Hla Htay (1997): Serpentinization of Webula ultramafic body, Falam Township, p.1-9.
- Hla Htay (1985): Mineralogy and Petrology of the Webula Ultramafic body and Kwekha Metamorphics, Falam Township, Unpub, M.Sc. (Thesis), Yangon University, p.298.
- Hla Htay (2002): The Mineralization of Ophiolite Belts in Myanmar, Journal of Myanmar Academy of Arts & Science, vol. 1, No.2.
- Hla Htay (2004): The Ophiolite Belt of Myanmar, Journal of the Geological Society of Thailand, No.1, May 2004, p.97-113.
- Hoskin, P.W.O., and Schaltegger, U., (2003): The composition of zircon and igneous and metamorphic petrogenesis, in Hanchar, J.M., and Hoskin, P.W.O., eds., Zircon: Reviews in Mineralogy and Geochemistry Volume 53, p. 27-62, doi:10.2113/0530027.
- Hutchison, C.S., (1975): Ophiolite in Southeast Asia, Geological Society of America Bulletin, vol.86, p.797-806.
- Mitchell, A.H.G, (1979): Geology and Exploration Geochemistry of part of the Northern and Southern Chill Hills and Arakan Yoma, Western Burma.
- Peters, T.J. (1968): Distribution of Mg, Fe, Al, Ca and Na in coexisting olivine orthopyroxene and clinopyroxene in the Totalp serpentinite (Davos, Switzerland) and in the alpine metamorphosed Malenco serpentinite (N.Italy). Contr. Mineral. Petrology, p.18,65-75.
- Rubatto, D., (2002): Zircon trace element geochemistry: Partitioning with garnet and the link between U-Pb ages and metamorphism: Chemical Geology, v. 184, p. 123-138.
- Thidar Win, Dr., (2014): Geology and Petrology of the Mwetaung-Yazagyo area, Tiddim Township, Chin State. Ph.D. Thesis, University of Mandalay.
- Wicks, F. J and Whittaker, E.J.W, (1977): Serpentine textures and serpentinization. Can. Mineral, vol.15, p. 459-488.

- Wicks, F. J. & Zussman, J. (1975): Microbeam X-ray diffraction patterns of the serpentine minerals. *Can. Mineral.* p.13,244-258.
- Varlakov, A. S. (1975): Stubachite, a special kind of dunite in alpine-type harzburgite massifs. *Int. Geol. Rev.* 16, 1205-1213.
- Win Swe (2012): Outline Geology and economic mineral occurrences of the Union of Myanmar, *Journal of the Myanmar Geosciences Society, Spe. Pub. No(1).* P.43,57,60.